

STRUCTURES AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF PVDF/GRAPHENE NANOCOMPOSITES PREPARED BY SOLUTION MIXING AND MELT-COMPRESSION

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1 Introduction

Poly(vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) is a thermoplastic material used in a variety of products and parts such as piezoelectric film, fiber, belt, and pipe. For advanced applications of PVDF, it is highly desirable to enhance and control its physical properties such as thermal stability, mechanical modulus, and electrical conductivity [1,2].

Accordingly, nano-sized materials such as silicates, multiwall-carbon nanotube, single wall-carbon nanotube, carbon black, graphite, silica, POSS, metal fibers and powders have been considered typical reinforcing fillers for polymeric nanocomposites with improved physical properties.

Among the reinforcing nano-materials, graphene platelets exhibit unique structural features and physical properties [3]. They have excellent mechanical strength, electrical conductivity, and thermal stability. Graphene platelet is structurally monolayer of carbon atoms arranged in 2-dimensional honeycomb lattice and it is stacked in graphite due to the van der Waals forces.

In this study, we have manufactured a series of PVDF-based nanocomposites by introducing graphene platelets, which are prepared by an acid-treatment and following rapid thermal expansion, and then investigated their structures, morphology, melting/crystallization behavior, thermal stability, mechanical and electrical properties as a function of graphene content.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

PVDF (fluorine content of 59%) was obtained from Scientific Polymer Products, Inc. Natural graphite flake was supplied from Sigma-Aldrich Com. N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF) was purchased from

Daejung Chemicals & Metals Co., Ltd. HNO₃ and H₂SO₄ were purchased from Junsei Chemical Com, Japan. KClO₃ was purchased from Kanto Chemical CO., Inc.

2.2 Preparation of Nanocomposites

Graphene platelets were prepared by acid-treatment and following rapid thermal heating of natural graphite flakes [4]. PVDF/graphene nanocomposites were prepared by solution mixing and melt-compression. Firstly, PVDF (20 g) was dissolved in DMF solvent (200 ml) and then the predetermined amount of graphene platelets was added. PVDF/graphene solutions were stirred for 1 hr and then ultra-sonicated for 1 hr. PVDF/graphene solutions were poured into water and then filtered. PVDF/graphene filtrates were dried and melt-compressed into film samples for structure and property analyses. The graphene contents in the nanocomposites were controlled to be 0.0~7.0 wt%. Accordingly, the nanocomposite film samples were named as PVDF/graphene_X, where X denotes the graphene content by wt% in the nanocomposites.

2.3 Characterization of Nanocomposites

Structural order and morphological features of the nanocomposites were characterized by using wide angle X-ray diffractometer and SEM, respectively. For obtaining SEM images, the nanocomposites films were cryogenically fractured in a liquid nitrogen bath and then coated with gold/palladium. Melting/crystallization behavior, thermal stability, dynamic mechanical property, and electrical resistivity of the neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposite films with various graphene contents were investigated by using DSC, TGA, DMA, and electrometer/high resistance meter, respectively.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Structural and Morphological Features of Nanocomposites

Fig. 1. SEM images of (A) neat PVDF, (B) PVDF/graphene_0.3, (C) PVDF/graphene_0.7, (D) PVDF/graphene_1.0, (E) PVDF/graphene_3.0, (F) PVDF/graphene_7.0.

To confirm the morphological features of graphene incorporated in the PVDF matrix, SEM images of the fractured surfaces for the nanocomposite films were examined, as can be seen in Fig. 1. The pristine PVDF film displays a smooth surface (Fig. 1A). In contrast, the rougher fractured surface was observed for PVDF/graphene nanocomposite films with higher graphene contents (Fig. 1B-F). PVDF/graphene nanocomposite films with 0.3 and 0.7 wt% graphene contents exhibit the rough fractured surfaces without aggregates of graphene sheets (Fig. 1B-C). It indicates that the graphene platelets are well dispersed in the PVDF matrix. However, partial aggregates of graphene platelets in the nanocomposites with higher graphene contents above 1.0 wt% were observed. Nonetheless, it was confirmed that the partial aggregates of graphene sheets are not in ordered crystalline state. As can be

seen in X-ray diffraction patterns of the nanocomposite films of Fig. 2, any diffraction peak associated with the ordered crystalline phase of graphene platelets was not detected, whereas typical diffraction peaks corresponding to PVDF α -form crystals were detected for all PVDF/graphene nanocomposite films. The strong diffraction peaks at $2\theta = 17.6, 18.5, 20.0,$ and 26.6° are assigned to be 100, 020, 100, and 021 reflections of the PVDF α -phase crystals, respectively.

Fig. 2. X-ray diffraction patterns of neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposites with various graphene contents.

3.2 Thermal Properties of Nanocomposites

In DSC cooling curves (Fig. 3), the melt-crystallization temperatures of PVDF/graphene nanocomposites shifted to higher temperatures with the increment of graphene content up to ~ 1.0 wt%. It demonstrates that graphene platelets serve as effective nucleating agents for PVDF α -form crystals and thus promoted the overall melt-crystallization rates of the nanocomposites. On the other hand, in cases of the nanocomposites with higher graphene contents above 1.0 wt%, the melt-crystallization peak temperatures were not changed, but the peak areas were slightly decreased with the graphene contents.

Fig. 4 presents TGA curves of neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposite films examined

under the oxygen gas condition. It was found that thermo-oxidative degradation temperatures of the nanocomposites were increased with increasing the graphene content up to 1.0 wt% and then decreased at higher graphene contents above 3.0 wt%. For the nanocomposite with 1.0 wt% graphene, typical thermo-oxidative degradation temperatures for 5% and 50% weight loss were characterized to be 423 and 450 °C, respectively, which were 52 and 20 °C higher than those of the neat PVDF, respectively. This noticeable enhancement in thermal stability of the nanocomposites is believed to originate from the presence of graphene platelets, which served as barriers to the permeating active oxygen gas through the PVDF matrix.

Fig. 3. DSC cooling thermograms of neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposites with various graphene contents.

Fig. 5 shows TGA curves of neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposites examined under the inert nitrogen gas condition. It was found that thermal decomposition temperatures of the nanocomposites were increased with increasing the graphene content up to 0.7 wt% and then decreased at higher graphene contents above 1.0 wt%. It is believed that the decrease in thermal decomposition temperatures for the nanocomposite films with higher graphene contents above 1.0 wt% is associated with the presence of aggregated graphene platelets.

Fig. 4. TGA curves of neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposites with various graphene contents under the oxygen gas condition.

Fig. 5. TGA curves of neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposites with various graphene contents under the nitrogen gas condition.

3.3 Mechanical Properties of Nanocomposites

To investigate the influence of graphene content on the mechanical properties of PVDF/graphene nanocomposites, dynamic storage modulus was measured as a function of temperature, as shown in Fig. 6. With increasing the temperature, the dynamic storage moduli decreased slightly from -50 to 150 °C, and they decreased rapidly above 150 °C due to the melting of PVDF crystals. When the

dynamic storage moduli at room temperature for PVDF/graphene nanocomposites were compared, they were significantly increased with the graphene content up to 3.0 wt%. It indicates that the graphene platelets dispersed in the nanocomposites act as mechanical reinforcing fillers for the PVDF matrix.

3.4 Electrical Properties of Nanocomposites

Fig. 7 displays electrical volume and surface resistivities of the nanocomposite films as a function of graphene content. The electrical resistivity of PVDF/graphene nanocomposites exhibited a pronounced transition from an insulator to nearly a semiconductor with the increment of graphene content. The electrical volume resistivity of the neat PVDF film was measured to be in the order of $\sim 10^{16}$ $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$. For PVDF/graphene nanocomposites, the electrical volume resistivity of remained almost unchanged at $\sim 10^{14}$ $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ up to ~ 1.0 wt% graphene and then decreased substantially to $\sim 10^6$ $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ at higher graphene contents above 1 wt%. This result can be satisfactorily explained by the percolation theory, i.e., the electrical conduction path of graphene platelets in the nanocomposites is formed at certain graphene content between 1.0 and 3.0 wt%. It is worthy to note that the electrical resistivity of $\sim 10^6$ $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ for the PVDF/graphene nanocomposites is low enough to attain the electrostatic dissipation and/or partial electromagnetic dissipation performances.

Fig. 6. Temperature-dependent dynamic storage moduli of neat PVDF and PVDF/graphene nanocomposite films with various graphene contents.

Fig. 7. Electrical volume and surface resistivities of PVDF/graphene nanocomposite films as a function of graphene content.

References

- [1] M. Tran, M. Shaffer and A. Bismarck “Manufacturing Carbon Nanotube/PVDF Nanocomposite Powders”. *Macromol. Mater. Eng.*, Vol. 293, pp 188-193, 2008.
- [2] S. Yu, W. Zheng, W. Yu, Y. Zhang, Q. Jiang and Z. Zhao “Formation Mechanism of β -Phase in PVDF/CNT Composite Prepared by the Sonication Method”. *Macromolecules*, Vol. 42, pp 8870-8874, 2009.
- [3] S. Stankovich, D. A. Dikin, G. B. Dommett, K. M. Kohlhaas, E. J. Zimney, E. A. Stach, R. D. Piner, S. T. Nguyen and R. S. Ruoff “Graphene-based composite materials”. *Nature*, Vol. 442, pp 282-286, 2006.
- [4] I.-H. Kim, Y. G. Jeong “Polylactide/Exfoliated Graphite Nanocomposites with Enhanced Thermal Stability, Mechanical Modulus, and Electrical Conductivity”. *J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Phys.*, Vol. 48, pp 850-858, 2010.